

Embodied Emissions: The Overlooked Carbon Footprint in Digital Research Infrastructure

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DRI lifecycle with embodied emissions outlined in red

Embodied emissions, (often referred to as ‘embodied carbon’ or sometimes ‘embedded carbon’) are the greenhouse gas emissions emitted during the gathering of raw materials, manufacture, transportation and later disposal of a device.

As hardware becomes more efficient and increasingly powered by renewable energy, the active emissions during use will shrink. If the carbon footprint of the supply chain is not tackled with the same urgency, this will make embodied carbon a larger proportion of the total footprint. Technology changes which reduce energy consumption in use can also increase the supply chain energy demand (e.g. the shift from spinning disks to solid state storage in personal computers). When evaluating the carbon footprint of a piece of Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI) equipment, embodied emissions are a key consideration and can make up a substantial part of the total emissions.

For user devices like laptops, which are now very energy efficient, embodied emissions will often outweigh the emissions during use¹.

For large facilities, embodied emissions can also include the embodied carbon of the buildings and equipment to hold the DRI as well as the infrastructure itself.

It is important to consider the relative lifetime of the equipment, a building may contain a large amount of embodied emissions compared to a laptop but has a much longer lifetime

¹ Jattke et al. 2020. “Environmental Implications of Service Life Extension of Mobile Devices”. <https://doi.org/10.21256/zhaw-20808>, Clément et al., 2020. Sources of variation in life cycle assessments of smartphones and tablet computers, Environmental Impact Assessment Review, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2020.106416>.

over which those embodied emissions are being used.² This is further reduced if the building is shared with other facilities.

Based on estimates of the typical hardware usage amongst UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) researchers and the number of researchers paid by UKRI (58,000), the Sustainable Computing consortium project³ concluded that desktop machines, laptops, local servers and small clusters contributions to UKRI emissions (including embodied carbon) are of the same order as the UKRI-managed facilities, and that therefore it is important to reduce the emissions from this aspect of UKRI research.

The collective contribution to carbon emissions from non-facility computing equipment (laptops to server rooms) is of the same order as that of UKRI managed facilities

Despite its importance, quantifying embodied emissions is a large challenge, and continues to be an area of ongoing research. Embodied carbon costs of compute equipment are hard to obtain and often generic in nature not relating to exact computer specifications. There are also aspects of embodied emissions of the DRI that are not under direct control of UKRI. However, we cannot reach Net Zero without addressing embodied carbon and there are still actions we can take to make the best use of the carbon contained within our DRI, in both the way we use and obtain equipment.

Procurement

Several recommendations that came from the Net Zero sandpit and consortium projects suggested embodied emissions data (or best estimates) should be gathered from suppliers in the procurement of DRI equipment and should be a required consideration for procurement evaluation scoring.

- ❖ **Consider the sustainability** and net zero aims of the supplier. While embodied carbon estimates are a challenge to obtain, many major suppliers of hardware are making significant commitments such as 100% renewable energy supply by 2030 or net zero by 2050⁴.
- ❖ **Take care** that embodied emissions, such as from the energy supply used to manufacture equipment, are not double counted. These are scope 3 emissions to UKRI but scope 2 for the manufacturer.
- ❖ **Involve hardware experts** in the procurement process to ensure that the full lifetime of the equipment and maximisation of the use of embodied carbon are both considered.

² Hays, J., Walton, N., Jackson, A., Mudaraddi, A., Packer, A., & Owen, R. A. (2023). IRISCAST: Final Report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7692451>

³ Wim Vanderbauwhede. (2023). Energy consumption of facility and non-facility computing equipment used by UKRI researchers. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8072018>

⁴ Intel Corporate Responsibility Report, 2021-22. <https://csrreportbuilder.intel.com/pdfbuilder/pdfs/CSR-2021-22-Full-Report.pdf> , TSMC Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures (TCFD) Report, 2020. https://esg.tsmc.com/download/file/TSMC_TCFD_Report_E.pdf

- ❖ **Maintain proportionality** between scrutiny of embodied carbon for procurement and the scale of the equipment being purchased so as not to burden the process. For user devices such as laptops, it may be very difficult to distinguish embodied emissions of one type over another, but we can still change the way we use devices to make the most of the embodied carbon. This last point is developed further in the next section.

DRI use

There are several ways we can make the most of embodied carbon in our current DRI use.

Optimising use

- ❖ Counterintuitively, moving to high utilisation of resources in DRI facilities can maximise the use of embodied carbon. This also reduces the need to expand new DRI infrastructure.

Extending equipment lifetime

- ❖ Extending the lifetime of current equipment also makes the most use of the embodied carbon and reduces the need to expand new DRI infrastructure.
- ❖ Sites can also consider delaying decommissioning of kit to extend the lifetime of DRI equipment to get the most out of the embodied carbon cost.
- ❖ Old equipment can be donated to others (e.g. schools) to maximise use and minimise waste.

Upgrading equipment considerations

- ❖ The increased capability of upgrading equipment needs to be weighed up against the environmental impact of doing so. Upgrading to more efficient equipment does not necessarily lead to reduced emissions if the increased efficiency is just treated as expanded capacity (the 'rebound' effect).
- ❖ Upgrading to more efficient equipment may save use-phase carbon emissions but embodied carbon makes up a large part of the total emissions and should also be taken into account.
- ❖ An environmental impact assessment of an upgrade should include the embodied carbon of both the new and old equipment.

Working with suppliers

- ❖ Working closely with suppliers to enable accurate analysis of life-cycle costs when obtaining new DRI equipment. Many suppliers are working towards their own net zero goals, choosing these suppliers and involving experts in the process can ensure embodied carbon throughout the lifecycle of DRI equipment is considered.

Data storage

- ❖ The choice of data storage medium (solid-state disk, conventional hard disk or magnetic tape) has an impact on the carbon efficiency of data storage.

- ❖ Magnetic tape has by far the lowest carbon emissions but data stored on tape is not immediately accessible. Moving “cold” data which is rarely accessed but is nevertheless indispensable to tape archives can make significant carbon savings.

Conclusion

Properly accounting for embodied carbon is a challenge, but an essential component of the UKRI journey to Net Zero. This challenge needs input from all users of the DRI, from laptop users to facility managers as we consider the way we make best use of embodied carbon. We can take actions to both maximise the use of embodied carbon within the current UKRI DRI and expand sustainably to minimise embodied emissions.

Supporting recommendations

A general discussion of the recommendations can be found in section 3.2 of the [Net Zero DRI Scoping Project's final technical report: Sustainability in Digital Research Infrastructure](#)⁵.

A full list of the recommendations can be found in Appendix 3 of the final report and in addition can be accessed via this [spreadsheet](#).

Recommendation 55: Embodied emissions data. Information on embodied emissions of technology offered should form part of any procurement of an HPC system.

Recommendation 75: Information on carbon impact of manufacturing and delivery

Recommendation 82: High utilisation required. Maximise the use of embodied emissions by moving to high utilisation of resources and consideration of the hardware lifecycle from procurement to grave.

Final Report 1.3.4: Use phase and embodied carbon - the IRISCAST case study

Final Report 1.3.5: It is clear that the embodied carbon footprint of HPC hardware is large, but reliable quantification is not possible at this stage.

Final Report 2.1.5: Embodied emissions are vitally important for everybody to understand.

⁵ Juckes, M., Bane, M., Bulpett, J., Cartmell, K., MacFarlane, M., MacRae, M., Owen, A., Pascoe, C., & Townsend, P. (2023). Sustainability in Digital Research Infrastructure: UKRI Net Zero DRI Scoping Project final technical report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199984>